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Comparative Effects of *Bacillus* Probiotic and Antibiotic on the Growth Performance of Indigenous Aseel Chickens

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Abstract

The comparative effects of two different feed additives (*Bacillus* probiotic and antibiotic growth promoter) on the growth performance of 720 native Aseel chickens maintained in Pakistan were investigated. Different strains of *Bacillus* were isolated from various regions of Pakistan and the strain with maximum bacitracin-producing ability (*Bacillus licheniformis* KT443923) was selected for use as a probiotic. The *B. licheniformis* probiotic (1 g/kg of feed) and the aminoglycoside antibiotic neomycin (4 g/kg of feed) were used as feed additives. After six weeks of experiment, total body weight, weight gain, feed conversion ratio (FCR), and feed intake were significantly ($P < 0.05$) different among the treatments. These feeds resulted in final mean body weights of 197, 173 and 147 g; mean weight gains of 156, 132 and 107 g; mean feed intakes of 711, 654 and 596 g; mean FCRs of 4.57 ± 0.25 , 4.92 ± 0.24 and 5.55 ± 0.34 , and mortality rates of 0.28%, 0.84% and 1.25%, respectively. The results demonstrated that the probiotic-treated birds had better growth performance and FCR than the antibiotic-treated and control birds. Based on the results of the present study, it can be concluded that replacing the antibiotic growth promoter (neomycin) with a *Bacillus* probiotic improves the growth performance of Aseel chickens.

Key words: Antibiotic, *Bacillus* probiotic, Chicken, Feed additive, Growth performance, Mortality

INTRODUCTION

Probiotics are live microorganisms, either yeasts or bacteria, when applied or ingested in sufficient amounts will confer specific health benefits to host animals (Fuller, 1989; Anil and Harjinder, 2007). In animal feed, probiotics are used as an alternative to antibiotics that are used as growth promoters. The use of antibiotics in animal feed as growth promoters and as disease prevention agents can lead to antibiotic resistance in animals and humans, resulting in failure of treatment when needed (Corpet, 1996; Williams and Heymann, 1998; Cartman and Ragione, 2004; Marshall and Levy, 2011).

In chickens the microbiome of the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) has an important role in the health of the

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host. This includes reducing and preventing colonization by pathogenic bacteria through competitive exclusion and the production of antibacterial substances (Clavijo and Flórez, 2018). The use of microorganisms as probiotics can reduce the period required for stability of the microbiota in hatched chickens. This regulation of microbiota can serve to improve weight gain, feed conversion ratio (FCR), immune competence and intestinal health of the chickens (Panda *et al.*, 2000). Probiotics have proven to be effective alternatives to antibiotics in poultry; they can be used in chicken feed safely and without any adverse effects on production parameters and immune status of the flock (Al-Khalaifa *et al.*, 2019).

Bacillus species have emerged as one type of probiotic for use in animal feeds (Elshagabee *et al.*, 2017), including an increasing popularity for enhancing growth, immunity and intestinal health in poultry (Grant *et al.*, 2018). There are various examples of studies using *Bacillus* species as probiotics in chicken feeds from all over the world (Wolfenden *et al.* 2010; Bai *et al.*, 2017; Cramer *et al.*, 2018; Gong *et al.*, 2018; Liu *et al.*, 2019; Mazanko *et al.*, 2018; Wang *et al.*, 2018; Zhen *et al.*, 2018; Atela *et al.*, 2019; Prazdnova *et al.*, 2019; Ramlucken *et al.*, 2019; Whelan *et al.*, 2019).

As far as we are aware, no such studies in the indigenous chickens of Pakistan have been reported, the most popular being the Aseel variety (Iqbal *et al.*, 2012; Jatoi *et al.*, 2014; Usman *et al.*, 2014). In this study from Pakistan, *Bacillus licheniformis* was utilized as a probiotic for enhancing the growth performance of Aseel chickens in comparison with the commercial aminoglycoside antibiotic neomycin. The growth performance of birds due to the inclusion of probiotic was compared with the antibiotic-fed birds.

MATHODOLOGY

Ethical approval

This study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the Center for Advanced Studies in Vaccinology and Biotechnology (CASVAB), University of Balochistan.

Strains of Aseel chicken

Four strains of Aseel chicken native in Pakistan, namely Lakha, Mushki, Mianwali and Peshawari, were used in this study.

Probiotic and antibiotic

In this six weeks study, two feed additives, a *Bacillus* probiotic (*B. licheniformis* KT443923) and the aminoglycoside antibiotic neomycin, were introduced for measuring their comparative effects on the growth performance, FCR and mortality of Aseel chickens. Neomycin was chosen as the antibiotic to use in this study due to easy availability in the local market and due to financial constraints, as compared to other commonly used antibiotic growth promoters such as bacitracin methylene disalicylate.

Culture of probiotic

The *Bacillus* probiotic used in this study was prepared at GC University Lahore, Pakistan. Inoculum was prepared by using the isolated strain of *B. licheniformis*. For this purpose, LB broth medium (50 ml) was prepared in a 250-ml conical flask and autoclaved at 121 °C, 15 lbs pressure for 20 minutes. The autoclaved medium was inoculated with *B. licheniformis* and incubated at 37 °C in a rotary shaker at 150 rpm overnight. On the next day, a 1% inoculum was added to LB broth (3 litres) as a working volume in a 7 litre fermentor (Bioflo110, New Brunswick Scientific USA). Various parameters (pH, temperature, agitation and aeration rate) were optimized and the biomass obtained was centrifuged and then lyophilized (Christ 1-4 LD lyophilizer).

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Environmental temperature

The study was carried out over six weeks in the months of January and February when the average maximum temperature was recorded as 22.0 °C and average minimum temperature was 11.4 °C.

Age and weight of chicks

A total of 720 day-old chicks with an average body weight of 29 g were kept in the same environment without any treatment for seven days in order for them to adapt to the environment. After seven days, each bird was weighed individually and the average body weight was 40 g.

Experimental protocol

After seven days, the 720 birds (360 male and 360 female) were randomly divided into two treatment groups and one control group, each containing 240 birds: i.e., control group (having no feed additive), antibiotic group (having 4 g neomycin/kg of feed) and probiotic group (having 1 g probiotic/kg of feed) in which the probiotic contained 5×10^{10} *B. licheniformis* KT443923/g.

Management

The experimental birds were maintained in suitable cages with 0.6 sq.ft./bird and the poultry house environment was well-ventilated and open-sided. Male and female birds were reared and fed separately in their relevant groups. Initially, birds were weighed and tagged individually for identification. In this way three different colored tags (white for control, red for antibiotic, green for probiotic) were attached to the birds and feed sacks were also tagged with the same relevant colours to make it easy for the attendant to supply feed. Water and feed were offered ad-libitum. Fresh and clean water was provided for drinking through nipples and the birds were exposed to both natural daylight and artificial light. The feed was composed and balanced according to the instructions of the National Research Council, where standard starter feed was used on days 1 to 18 of chicks age, then grower feed was used on days 19 to 42 (National Research Council, 1994; Kidd *et al.*, 1998; Summers and Leeson, 2005).

Growth performance

The growth performance of the birds was studied as body weight (g), weight gain (g), feed intake (g) and FCR, which were all recorded. The weight of any dead birds was used to adjust feed consumption.

Statistical analysis

The data were analyzed by analysis of variance (ANOVA) techniques (Steel *et al.*, 1997) using SAS 9.1 (2002-03) portable software. Means were compared using Duncan's multiple range test (Duncan, 1955).

RESULTS

Body weight

At the end of the six weeks study, the average body weight of the birds supplemented with the probiotic and antibiotic differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) from each other and from the control (Table 1). Birds supplemented with the probiotic had an average body weight (197 g) that was significantly higher than birds supplemented with the antibiotic (172 g), which was also higher than in the control group (147 g). Overall, male birds (189 g) were 17.34% heavier than female birds (156 g), which is normal in the indigenous Aseel chicken population. The average weight comparison of the birds in the control group with the two treatment groups indicated that both the antibiotic and the probiotic were effective in increasing body weights of Aseel chickens. The *Bacillus*

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probiotic was more effective than the antibiotic in promoting body weight growth.

Weight gain

After six weeks, the weight gain in Aseel chickens was considerably higher in the probiotic-treated group (156 g) than in the antibiotic-treated group (132 g) and greater than the control group (107 g). Male birds had a 20.67% greater overall average weight gain (147 g) than female birds (117 g) at the end of six weeks (Table 2).

Feed intake

As well as body weight gain, feed intake is an important factor that affects the FCR of a poultry flock. The feed taken by both male and female Aseel chickens during the six week experiment supplemented with *Bacillus* probiotic and antibiotic varied significantly ($P < 0.05$). The probiotic-treated group consumed the greatest quantity of feed (711 g) compared with the antibiotic-treated group (654 g) and the control group (596 g). Female chickens overall consumed significantly less feed (579 g) than male chickens (728 g). Hence, *Bacillus* probiotic was noted as a useful appetizer during the study where the birds of this group improved their digestibility, which resulted in consumption of extra feed and birds consumed it more efficiently than those birds in the antibiotic and control groups (Table 3).

Feed conversion ratio

The FCR (g of feed/gain) is an important factor that determines the profitability of a poultry flock. The probiotic-treated group had the most efficient FCR of 4.57 ± 0.25 compared with the antibiotic-treated group (4.92 ± 0.24) and control group (5.55 ± 0.34). The overall FCR values for male (5.00 ± 0.56) and female (5.03 ± 0.42) chickens were not significantly different from each other (Table 4).

Mortality

The overall mortality was 2.35%, of which 1.25% was in the control group, 0.84% in the antibiotic-treated group and 0.28% in the probiotic-treated group. Mortality came from different varieties of the chickens. The very low mortality rate in the probiotic-treated chickens is an encouraging result for improving flock profitability.

DISCUSSION

Our study found that the mean body weights of three different treated groups of Aseel chickens (*Bacillus* probiotic-treated, antibiotic-treated, control) were significantly different ($P < 0.05$) after a six weeks experiment. The results demonstrated that probiotic and antibiotic supplements in feed are useful growth factors for Aseel chickens and the probiotic was most effective for enhancing feed consumption and utilization of the feed. These observations agree with previous studies by Kabir (2004) and Jatoi *et al.* (2014). Administration of probiotic to turkeys increased the average daily body weight and improved turkey production (Torres-Rodriguez *et al.*, 2007). The mechanisms by which probiotic microorganisms improve the FCR in animals is due to alteration in intestinal micro biota, an increase in growth rate of non-pathogenic facultative Gram-positive and anaerobic bacteria, which form hydrogen peroxide and lactic acid, as well as suppressing growth of intestinal pathogens. Probiotics also increase nutrient utilization as well as nutrient digestion (Yeo and Kim, 1997).

The antibiotic neomycin is currently being used as a feed additive to act as a growth promoter. In our study mortality was 0.28% in the probiotic-supplemented group, 0.84% in the antibiotic-treated group and 1.25% in the control group over six weeks duration of the experiment. Other than the test antibiotic neomycin, no other antibiotic treatment was given to the birds, although they were vaccinated. In one study, the effects of a probiotic on pathogens of the intestine were described, where probiotic inhibition by competition for nutrients,

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compounds like volatile fatty acids, toxic condition production and, low pH and bacteriocin, competition of probiotic and pathogens for binding sites on the intestinal epithelium and stimulation of immune system was explained (Patterson and Burkholder, 2003).

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study it can be concluded that *Bacillus* probiotic supplementation in poultry feed increases bird weight. *Bacillus* probiotic can be used to replace antibiotic growth promoters (neomycin) in Aseel chickens.

Ethical declaration

All experiments were carried out in accordance with the UK Animals (Scientific Procedures) Act (1986) and associated guidelines, and EU Directive 2010/63/EU for animal experiments.

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Tables

Table 1

Final mean body weights (\pm SEM) of male and female Aseel chickens as affected by probiotic- and antibiotic-supplemented feeds compared with control (after six weeks of experimentation).

	Male	Female	Mean for group
Control	164.67 \pm 5.74 g ^c	129.29 \pm 6.04 g ^d	146.98 \pm 4.86 g ^c
Antibiotic	189.96 \pm 7.66 g ^b	155.00 \pm 7.27 g ^c	172.48 \pm 5.81 g ^b
Probiotic	211.38 \pm 7.08 g ^a	183.58 \pm 6.31 g ^b	197.48 \pm 5.11 g ^a
Mean for sex	188.67 \pm 4.52 g ^a	155.96 \pm 4.57 g ^b	-

For each entry n = 120. Means with the same superscript letters in the table (column and row) do not differ significantly ($P < 0.05$).

Table 2

Final mean weight gains (\pm SEM) of male and female Aseel chickens as affected by probiotic- and antibiotic-supplemented feeds compared with control (after six weeks of experimentation).

	Male	Female	Mean for group
Control	122.92 \pm 5.40 g ^c	90.46 \pm 6.50 g ^c	106.69 \pm 4.80 g ^c
Antibiotic	148.54 \pm 7.53 g ^b	115.96 \pm 6.83 g ^b	132.25 \pm 5.56 g ^b
Probiotic	169.17 \pm 6.74 g ^a	143.13 \pm 6.37 g ^a	156.15 \pm 4.96 g ^a
Mean for sex	146.87 \pm 4.38 g ^a	116.51 \pm 4.53 g ^b	-

For each entry n = 120. Means with the same superscript letters in the table (column and row) do not differ significantly ($P < 0.05$).

Table 3

Final means of feed intake (\pm SEM) for male and female Aseel chickens as affected by probiotic- and antibiotic-supplemented feeds compared with control (after six weeks of experimentation).

	Male	Female	Mean for group
Control	694.90 \pm 33.43 g ^a	571.44 \pm 38.12 g ^b	595.79 \pm 28.94 g ^b
Antibiotic	736.41 \pm 42.03 g ^a	571.44 \pm 35.45 g ^b	653.92 \pm 29.74 g ^{ab}
Probiotic	754.09 \pm 30.96 g ^a	668.82 \pm 31.11 g ^a	711.46 \pm 22.58 g ^a
Mean for sex	728.47 \pm 20.58 g ^a	578.98 \pm 21.61 g ^b	-

For each entry n = 120. Means with the same superscript letters in the table (column and row) do not differ significantly ($P < 0.05$).

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Table 4

Final means of feed conversion ratio (FCR) (\pm SEM) for male and female Aseel chickens as affected by probiotic- and antibiotic-supplemented diets compared with control (after six weeks of experimentation).

	Male	Female	Mean for group
Control	5.64 \pm 0.34 ^a	5.46 \pm 0.32 ^b	5.55 \pm 0.34 ^a
Antibiotic	4.92 \pm 0.27 ^c	4.92 \pm 0.21 ^c	4.92 \pm 0.24 ^b
Probiotic	4.46 \pm 0.20 ^e	4.67 \pm 0.25 ^d	4.57 \pm 0.25 ^c
Mean for sex	5.00 \pm 0.56	5.03 \pm 0.42	-

For each entry n = 120. Means with the same superscript letters in the table (column and row) do not differ significantly ($P < 0.05$).